

Civic Education From Early–step Child and Civic Regulations

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Abstract – The subject of civic education covers the relevant aspects of the rights and obligations of citizens for social welfare; where the knowledge, experiences, skills, attitudes and values of the population can be involved, with the main objective of generating a society where cordiality, mutual support, respect and healthy coexistence exist. The term civic education comes from the word *civicus*, which means cordial relationship between people. This research theme contemplates the analysis of the way people act and relate, focusing on the children of the initial stage, who live with the educational agents in the classroom of the educational institutions of our country, essentially in the school where I work.

Keywords: Civic training, boys and girls in the initial stage, educational institutions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The behavior of every society is based on regulations for a cordial coexistence, which contains the ten main civic values also called ethical (respect, tolerance, responsibility, kindness, gratitude, humility, solidarity, commitment, trust and fairness), in addition to inclusion social, gender equality and support for society, and moral values (behavior and attitude) are also considered. Both types of values are an essential part of the family, where parents must be very attentive to what they reflect in their homes and must act in the most optimal way because their children in the initial stage are like a sponge that everything, they absorb it and are very dynamic and visual in the learning process in family homes, schools and in any other space where they live. If the process of exercising the application of civic training with both values is not carried out, societies could not coexist in a healthy way, so that social and economic development, especially, would not be adequate and at any time differences could be generated between people and at the society level, it would deteriorate little by little, until it disappeared. This could happen, as according to experts in the field of sociology, some civilizations have become extinct due to the lack of the exercise of civic and moral values.

1.1 Self-reflection analysis

Self-reflection is a process in which each person can self-evaluate in order to improve their qualities, abilities, behavior, abilities, which are part of the application of civic and moral values; that are very useful in the integral development of each person. In this case, each educational agent can know their strengths and weaknesses in their activities in school institutions, with the aim of improving their skills, qualities, abilities, behavior, and thus be able to better understand, carry out affective support and be able to participate in the solution. of some complicated situation of infants in the initial stage, with whom they live in the schools of the initial stage or Child Care Centers (CAI). It is essential to recognize the errors that are

made to prevent them from being replicated and causing a critical situation with children in the initial stage, which may have a negative effect on the integrity of infants in this stage. In this investigative analysis, this relevant aspect is evaluated in conjunction with some reflective evaluation questions, regarding early-stage education.

1.2 Educational activities with civic regulations

The development of activities in educational institutions of the initial stage, entails understanding the methodologies of the teaching–learning process to be used, developed by the Ministry of Public Education (SEP), and applied by educational agents with the specialized methods required to favor the integral development of children in the initial stage. One of the important aspects is that the educational agent develops self-reflection, with which he can delve into his family, as well as the participation actions in a personal way in educational courses and to know himself as much as possible regarding his emotions, needs and personal motivations. In addition, the weaknesses, strengths, defense mechanisms and purposes of his personal life can be evaluated, indicating that he may have the qualities, capacities, behavior, skills for coexistence with infants in the initial stage, who are becoming more visual in their process of learning, they immediately replicate what they observe and, on occasions, they contemplate actions in complicated situations within the family.

1.3 Self-reflection process

In this type of personal analysis, you can understand various types of failures or errors that are made in a personalized way and thus evaluate them so as not to make them again. This is achieved as awareness is raised regarding the process of continuous improvement in each person. Based on that, certain questions are determined that are mentioned below regarding this relevant topic and that is related to civic and moral values, which come from the family, personal and educational institutions:

1. What does “fear of others” refer to in the context of civility?

This important aspect is related to the fears that may arise regarding the proper application of civic and moral values, where educational agents must consider ethical values, referring to the work activities of their profession with optimal performance. and dignified treatment of people. This involves the basic values of honesty, responsibility, respect for the people who surround the educational agent from infants in the initial stage, co-workers, managerial and administrative staff, and parents with whom they have links for the improvement of children and initial stage girls, who are in charge of classrooms and schoolyards. On occasions, it is considered that these fears in the context of civility can create barriers in educational agents, thinking that what they do could be outside of the actions of civic and moral values.

2. How do we learn and acquire values, civic or otherwise?

The civic and moral values, in addition to the ethical values that educational agents commit to at the time of taking their professional ethics oath, come mainly from the family, where it is considered that each person can reinforce them in a personalized way, by being in connection with a complex society today and that sometimes due to that complexity, thoughts may arise that are part of not wanting to apply civic and moral values, with the aim of achieving a goal quickly and easily, such as applying bribes and corruption, breaking the rules of civility and the aforementioned values. In addition, educational institutions have focused to a large extent to consider this topic relevant and be applied as topics of subjects taught in

schools and considered by the SEP as vitally important for adequate training of human resources by educational agents.

3. Why in our personal and social actions do we commonly not apply ethics, awareness and civic responsibility and the focus of the common good?

This can sometimes occur in people who are not in control of their emotions and want immediate and easy results. In addition, a certain part of the population of any part of the world, having the ease of having a pleasant life due to a good situation of economic resources, feels the desire and the mentality that, with money, any action can be carried out at any price and believe they have the power of decision for others. This mentality sometimes causes abuses to the population or to people who are close family or relatives, close friends or coworkers, indicating that they can do what they want regardless of the fact that they can break the rules of civility and the civic, moral and ethical values. There have been cases of well-known professionals, but with an action, where they do not apply ethics, they can generate critical situations that can get involved with people who carry out illegal activities, thinking of receiving payment for some inappropriate action, without expecting that they can harm those people, families or close friends.

4. How is self-realization connected to the common good? List some possibilities and give an example.

This important aspect must be elaborated to achieve the common good of the people that surround us, and of a complex society, as long as the objectives and efficient planning of the activities to be carried out to achieve the desired goals have been elaborated based on the skills, qualities, behavior and capacities of each person and if the support of someone specialized in any subject is necessary, consider their help, even when it is necessary to prepare some payment for their services. This is better than looking for ways to generate inappropriate, illegal, and inappropriate actions that you don't need to do. An example may be that in the case of a person carrying out some government procedure and having a relative in a government agency. In this case, the person who carries out the procedure wants his procedure to be carried out quickly, regardless of whether he arrived early or late, and without respecting the people who arrived before him and not participating in a line of government procedures.

5. Define social cohesion and explain why it is relevant to civility.

This concept of interest in a society refers to the functionality of a society as a whole, where it takes into account relevant aspects such as social inclusion, behavior of the people of a community or society, as well as the urban rules that relate to those people. This is important, because if the rules of civility are complied with, as well as civic, moral and ethical values; Society can be linked in an orderly manner and without presenting complicated situations between people. But, if there are cases of breaking the rules of civility and civic, moral and ethical values, society becomes very complex and difficult for people to live with. This is why it is important in the concept of civility, with the aim of achieving a healthy coexistence among the members of all the populations of the world and between each population.

6. Explain in your own word's Lévinas' maxim: "I am loved, I am named, therefore I am".

According to this philosopher, this phrase refers to thinking first of the other or of the people that surround me, before taking any action on my part, where it is assumed that the people that surround me, who may be close relatives or family relatives or close friends, or even more, people I don't know can be affected by any action or decision made by a person, without considering what may affect those around them. This sometimes occurs when there is no adequate control of emotions, and certain people wish to develop some actions that could corrupt the rules of civility and civic, moral and ethical values. In the case of an

educational agent, they should always think about the infants in their initial stage, with whom they live in the classroom or school yards, before taking any action that could harm them.

7. Why is responsibility one of the most important civic values –and other types– for the human person and society?

This relevant value, which is part of what parents should instill in their children, especially those in the initial stage, who learn very quickly in a visual way, replicating what they see in their family and in other places, which even being inadequate actions cannot understand, but it is explained to them that they should not be carried out. The sense of responsibility is very important in any activity, even when it is sometimes necessary to carry out activities that lead to a double or triple effort or actions, one must be responsible and carry them out efficiently, without breaking the rules of civility. and civic, moral and ethical values. This is of great interest to each person, because it makes itself known as it is before carrying out the activities that can be assigned and meet the goals in a personalized and group way before a society or community, and be part of the optimal development of a society. As an educational agent, the sense of responsibility for caring for early-stage infants and achieving maximum school performance is important.

8. Make an argument by which the private good is reconciled with the common good.

Elaborating the common good must be linked to the private good, because it must be considered that meeting personalized goals should not affect any person who surrounds who wishes to achieve the fulfillment of their particular objectives, which lead to the improvement of any of the actions such as skills, abilities, aptitudes and conduct. It is always to think that if I want to develop some improvement of some strategy of the teaching–learning process as an educational agent, I must think that a situation cannot occur that could compromise the integrity of the children with whom the educational agent lives, considering the situation to always achieve improvement as a common good and achieve personalized goals.

9. Is the exercise of good citizenship (or ethical citizenship) the key to the survival of humanity? Explain the reason for your answer.

This type of exercise is vital for the efficient linkage between the citizens of a community or society, because on the basis of this optimal human relations are built between the members of the societies, indicating that it is relevant for the survival and continuity of generations of a citizenry that is interested in achieving a healthy coexistence, following the rules of civility and civic, moral and ethical values. As an educational agent, it is considered to promote in the children of the initial stage, that the rules of urbanity, and civic, moral and ethical values, are fulfilled in an efficient way, to achieve the necessary agreements and a healthy coexistence in a community or society.

10. The establishment of civic and ethical codes is a basis for maintaining a harmonious and fair world, among other things, but what is needed for these codes to be applied to reality? Give at least 2 arguments.

Establishing civic and ethical codes is of great importance in any society or community, from there it is based that they must be complied with and ensure that the members of a society live in harmony, starting from the family bosom of the parents of family with their children, especially in the initial stage, who are beginning a life and must be considered in all actions of the family and society. This is of great relevance, because to achieve links between the individuals of a community in a cordial and harmonious way. But sometimes some people want to break these civic and ethical codes, and with this an imbalance in society

begins to arise, which can lead to differences between people or even some critical situation such as fights between family members. and society, which may affect infants in the initial stage. It is there where the educational agent can participate with the control of the emotions of the infants of this step.

2. METHODOLOGY

This investigation was made to evaluate the case of civic regulations from the child early-step, obtaining relevant information to determine that the civic regulations and moral regulations in home from fathers, are very important to have an harmonic society.

3. RESULTS

To prepare table, I self-reflected on my actions as a stay-at-home mother, a person in the society where I live, an educational agent, to know my weaknesses and strengths and to be able to improve my strengths and gradually eliminate my weaknesses, mainly as an educational agent where I have the opportunity to live with infants of the initial stage. This is why I express my self-reflection in table 1, where my opinions are shown regarding how I consider myself in the subject of civic and ethical values.

Table -1: Personal opinion of civic and ethical values

Concept	Valoration			Explication
	0	1	2	
1. How I behave with my family			X	I consider that my behavior with my family has been pleasant and cordial, even when I have had moments with certain types of complicated situations, which have been resolved, as part of the respect and healthy coexistence
2. How is my attitude towards the society where I live			X	I honestly feel that it is cordial and respectful, with a healthy and brief coexistence.
3. How do my initial stage students consider me?			X	By providing affective support to the initial stage students, with whom I live, I feel that there is a healthy relationship with the boys and girls and the parents of the infants in the initial stage, with whom I live at the school where I work, as part of the responsibility as an educational agent.
4. I consider that I have developed some activity to improve my abilities, attitude, behavior and skills to develop a dignified and cordial treatment with the initial stage students with whom I currently live			X	I consider that I have tried to achieve an optimal behavior with the best attitude for living with the initial stage students, with whom I have lived, and have worked for 20 years, as part of affective support.
5. I consider that I have taken advantage of complicated			X	I feel that, in my life, I have gone through complicated situations and I have overcome

situations in my daily life to gain experience and achieve more goals in my personal life				them, contemplating that they have made me stronger and with this I have taken advantage of these situations as a personal experience, being important in my commitment as a mother of a family, a socially cordial person and an agent educational.
6. I consider that my life with my family is pleasant and cordial?			X	I consider that I have tried to achieve a healthy and cordial coexistence, with some complicated situations, which have been resolved and taken from personal and family experience, such as the kindness of a healthy coexistence
7. Do I consider that I have improved my strategies in the teaching-learning process?			X	I feel that, if I have improved and made significant advances in the initial stage students with whom I have lived and currently live, and these career courses have improved my approach to dignified and cordial treatment that I had before starting, being part of My personal commitment to be better every day.
8. Do I feel that the relationship with my managers and co-workers is healthy?			X	I consider that if I have a healthy relationship with some complications on certain occasions that have been solved.
Conclusions of my self-reflection				I consider myself a person who has overcome challenges and another of them is the completion of this relevant career, from which I have learned a lot. I feel that my actions have improved my control of emotions as part of the kindness, commitment, inclusion and socially cordial person.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this investigative work of self-reflection, it supported me to reinforce the civic formation that I exercise every day, from my home, the society where I live daily and as an educational agent in my school activities, with infants in the initial stage, managers and coworkers. It is of great relevance to consider civic and moral values on a daily basis, and it is part that I instill in my family, infants with whom I live and parents. This informative analysis is of great relevance with the questions and their answers, which can contribute to the improvement of a more efficient educational process, than is predicted in all schools in our country. In addition, the control of emotions can be contemplated, to be patient, prudent and tolerant in each action to be carried out, respecting other people and the times required for each action. Sometimes, certain types of possibilities may arise, that a person may have some type of benefit, such as considering that someone's goals can be achieved, supported by a family member or friend who is performing some function in a place where it was made, for example, procedures of any kind.

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